

CALCULATING INTEGRALS USING EULER INTEGRALS

Orazbekova Dilbar

Master’s student at Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajinyoz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15292354>

Annotation. In this thesis, some complex integrals in mathematical analysis are solved using Euler integrals.

Key words: Integral, Euler integral, Gamma function, symmetric matrix.

Annotatsiya. Bu tezisdagi matematik analizdagi bazi bir murakkab integrallar Eyler integrallari yordamida hisoblangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Integral, Eyler integrali, Gamma funksiya, simmetrik matritsa

Аннотация. В данном тезисе рассматриваются способы решения некоторых сложных интегралов математического анализа с использованием интегралов Эйлера.

Ключевые слово: Интеграл, интеграл Эйлера, гамма-функция, симметричная матрица.

In the course of mathematical analysis, we widely use the methods of calculating definite integrals when calculating improper integrals. However, we encounter several problems when calculating some integrals with these methods.

In such cases, using Euler integrals gives a good result. We will consider this in the following two examples.

Example 1. Given a parametric view

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(1+x^2)^\alpha} dx \quad (\alpha > 0)$$

calculate the integral.

Solving: First we calculate the $x = tg(\arcsin \sqrt{y})$ permutation,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(1+x^2)^\alpha} dx = 2 \int_0^1 \frac{1}{(1+tg^2(\arcsin \sqrt{y}))^\alpha} \cdot \frac{1}{2\sqrt{y}(1-y)^{\frac{3}{2}}} dy = \int_0^1 y^{\frac{1}{2}-1} (1-y)^{(\alpha-\frac{1}{2})-1} dy \quad (1)$$

we will have equality. This equation can be written in

$$B(1/2, \alpha - 1/2) = \int_0^1 y^{\frac{1}{2}-1} (1-y)^{(\alpha-\frac{1}{2})-1} dy$$

using Euler's integral of the first kind (beta function) and using Euler's integral of the second kind (gamma function) ([1,2]) we get the following result:

$$B(1/2, \alpha - 1/2) = \int_0^1 y^{\frac{1}{2}-1} (1-y)^{(\alpha-\frac{1}{2})-1} dy = \frac{\Gamma(1/2)\Gamma(\alpha-1/2)}{\Gamma(\alpha)} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(\alpha-1/2)}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$$

In the special case when $\alpha = 1$: $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{1+x^2} dx = \pi$

Example 2: $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ax^2 + 2bx + c)^\alpha} dx$. $a > 0, b^2 - 4ac < 0, \alpha > \frac{1}{2}$.

calculate the integral.

Solving: First, we write the square root of $ax^2 + 2bx + c$ in perfect square form, giving us the equation

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ax^2 + 2bx + c)^\alpha} dx = \left(\frac{a}{ac - b^2}\right)^\alpha \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{dx}{\left(1 + \frac{a^2}{ac - b^2} \left(x + \frac{b}{a}\right)^2\right)^\alpha}. \quad (2)$$

This improper integral has the form of the previous integral. In this integral, we also get the result below by trying to use $\frac{a}{\sqrt{ac - b^2}} \left(x + \frac{b}{a}\right) = \operatorname{tg}(\arcsin \sqrt{y})$.

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ax^2 + 2bx + c)^\alpha} dx = \left(\frac{a}{ac - b^2}\right)^\alpha \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{dx}{\left(1 + \frac{a^2}{ac - b^2} \left(x + \frac{b}{a}\right)^2\right)^\alpha} =$$

$$\left(\frac{a}{ac - b^2}\right)^\alpha \frac{\sqrt{ac - b^2}}{a} \int_0^1 y^{\frac{1}{2}-1} (1 - y)^{(\alpha - \frac{1}{2})-1} dy = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \left(\frac{a}{ac - b^2}\right)^{\alpha - \frac{1}{2}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(\alpha - \frac{1}{2})}{\Gamma(\alpha)}.$$

Now from the known formula ([3,5]) $(\alpha > \frac{n+1}{4})$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 + x_1^2 + \dots + x_{n-1}^2)^{1-2\alpha} dx_1 \dots dx_{n-1} = \pi^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha - \frac{n+1}{2})}{\Gamma(2\alpha - 1)},$$

and results (1), (2), we arrive at the

following proof ([4]):

Theorem. If $\alpha > \frac{n}{2}$, then

$$I_n(\alpha) = \int_T \frac{T}{(\det(I + T^2))^\alpha} = 2^{\frac{n(n-1)}{4}} \pi^{\frac{n(n+1)}{4}} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha - \frac{n}{2})}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \prod_{\nu=1}^{n-1} \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha - \frac{n+\nu}{2})}{\Gamma(2\alpha - \nu)}.$$

Here $T = (t_{jk})_1^n$ runs through all real symmetric matrices of order n , and $T = 2^{\frac{n(n-1)}{4}} \prod_{j < k} dt_{jk}$.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАННАЯ ЛИТЕРАТУРА

1. Т. Азларов, Х. Мансуров, «Математик анализ», Тошкент. «Ўзбекстон», 1995.-279 б
2. А. Саъдуллаев. «Математик анализ курсидан мисол ва масалалар тўплами», 2-к, Тошкент. «Ўзбекстон», 1995.-236 б
3. Шабат Б.В. Введение в комплексный анализ. // Ч.2. – М.: Наука, 1985. – 464 с.
4. Хуа Ло-Кен. «Гармонический анализ функций многих комплексных переменных в классических областях». М.: 1959 г.
5. У. Рудин. «Теория функций в единичном шаре из \square^n ». М.: Мир, 1984г.